

A Critical Study on Business Strategies of WIPRO

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Abstract

Wipro limited is leading international info technology, consulting and business method services company. we have a tendency to harness the facility of psychological feature computing, hyper-automation, robotics, cloud, analytics and rising technologies to assist our clients adapt to the digital world and make them booming. an organization recognized globally for its comprehensive portfolio of services, a powerful commitment to sustainability and good company citizenship, we've over 160,000 dedicated employees serving clients across six continents. Together, we have a tendency to discover concepts and connect the dots to build a much better and a bold new future. we have a tendency to began our business as a vegetable oil manufacturer in 1945 at Amalner, a small city in Western india and thereafter, forayed into soaps and other client care products. during the first 1980s, we have a tendency to entered the Indian IT industry by manufacturing and selling minicomputers. within the 1990s, we have a tendency to leveraged our hardware R&D design and software system development experience and started providing computer code services to international shoppers. In 2013, we have a tendency to demerged the non-IT distributed Businesses. With a data of over 25 years in IT Services, we are, today, targeted entirely on the global information Technology business. Wipro is listed on the National stock exchange and Mumbai stock exchange in india and new york stock exchange in the U.S.A.

In this paper, we have identified and analyzed various alternative finance models in india and discussed the possible advantages, benefits, constraints in addition as disadvantages of such facilities from different stakeholder's purpose of read. we have a tendency to also compared the alternative finance models with traditional banking and capital market finance and urged the possibility to be used to take advantages of such options in large-scale business investments.

Keywords: Capital market, Alternative finance, Types of alternative finance, ABCD analysis of alternative finance

1. INTRODUCTION :

The company was incorporated on 29 December 1945 in Amalner, Maharashtra by Mohamed Premji as "Western India Vegetable Products Limited", later abbreviated to "Wipro". ... On 7

June 1977, the name of the company changed from Western India Vegetable Products Limited, to Wipro Products Limited. It was initially set up as a manufacturer of vegetable and refined oils in Mumbai, under the trade names of kisan, Sunflower and Camel.

Wipro is one of India's largest publicly traded companies and 7th largest IT services firm in the world. Wipro Limited is a leading global information technology, consulting and business process services company. We harness the power of cognitive computing, hyper-automation, robotics, cloud, analytics and emerging technologies to help our clients adapt to the digital world and make them successful. A company recognized globally for its comprehensive portfolio of services, strong commitment to sustainability and good corporate citizenship, we have over 160,000 dedicated employees serving clients across six continents. Together, we discover ideas and connect the dots to build a better and a bold new future

2.OBJECTIVES :

- To analyze the overall Growth of the company
- To find the Services and Products provided by the company
- To find the Corporate Social Responsibility of the company
- To Check the different Solution for improving the Growth of the company.

3.SMART PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

The key components of the hardware industry are servers, desktops, notebooks and tablet computers, storage devices, peripherals, printers and networking equipment. According to the NASSCOM Report, the hardware segment of the IT-Business Process Management exports from India is estimated to be \$15 billion in fiscal year 2018. Emergence of cloud computing technologies is negatively affecting demand for IT products such as servers. Fast-evolving technology landscapes, dynamic economic environments and the emergence of digital business has created a need for enterprises to look for a partner to advise, design and execute their technology transformation and support programs. Large multinational enterprises are engaging global IT Services companies who can deliver high quality service on a global scale and at competitive costs. Over the past two decades, with the emergence of the internet and inexpensive connectivity, the global delivery model of service delivery has risen to become the preferred model in sourcing of IT services, business process services and technology infrastructure services research and development services. In this period, service providers have gained technological expertise, domain competency and delivery capability by either developing organically or by acquiring companies with these competencies. Large multinational enterprises are engaging global IT Services companies to deliver high quality service on a global scale and at competitive costs. We believe the IT Services industry has significant growth potential.

4.CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY :

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has become one of the leading topics of discussion at World Economic Forum Meetings in the last decade and more. It is basically the initiatives an organisation undertakes to positively influence the society in which it exists.

WIPRO ACTIVITIES:

4.1. WIPRO CARES

- “Wipro Cares” strives hard to address major issue responsibly. From community relief and rehabilitation in times of disasters to education opportunities, health and wellness programs for the needy, we make sure that our social initiatives touch every level of society that needs our help.
- Wipro care is an initiative by the wiproites.
- Wipro care contributes through two prolonged strategy. Learning enhancement & disaster rehabilitation.

4.2.ECO EYE

- To strike a balance with environment ,we formed Eco Eye a few years ago to bring all our green initiatives under one banner, and to incorporate better ecological balance in every project we execute.
- Aims to promote.
- Initiatives undertaken in direction of environment saving.
- Inter connection of sewer line.
- Biogas plant.
- Rainwater harvesting
- Eco-friendly chemical

5.CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS :

Wipro believes in creating value for the customer over and above the contracted terms. Our approach is based on our vision of delivering value to our customer businesses based on a solid relationship of trust, collaboration and competence. We ensure this by providing solutions that integrate deep industry insights, leading technologies and best in class delivery processes. Engagement is critical to meet and understand the expectations of customers. The key to customer retention is building deep relationships. IT industry, a major driver of efficiency and productivity improvements for most businesses, is undergoing tremendous change in the face of disruptive technologies. The Business Strategy section outlines the drivers and how it informs our business model, offerings and customer engagement approach.

Some of the customers of Wipro are :

- IAF
- Airtel
- CITI Bank
- NIC
- MetLife
- DIAL
- BHEL
- BSNL
- Quicker
- Indian army

6.COMPETATORS :

- Tata practice services(company)
- Infosys restricted
- HCL Technologies
- Tech mahindra
- Larsen & Turbo Infotech
- Syntel(company)
- Mphasis(company)
- Zensar Technologiess
- Mindtree(company)

7.FINANCE :

Financial performance	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
Revenue [®]	437,628	473,182	516,307	554,179	546,359
Profit before Depreciation, Amortization, Interest and Tax	100,460	108,246	111,825	116,986	105,418
Depreciation and Amortization	11,106	12,823	14,965	23,107	21,124
Profit before Interest and Tax [†]	89,354	95,423	96,860	93,879	84,294
Profit before Tax [†]	101,005	111,683	114,933	110,356	102,474
Tax	22,600	24,624	25,366	25,213	22,390
Profit after Tax - attributable to equity holders [†]	77,967	86,528	89,075	84,895	80,081
Per share data					
Earnings Per Share- Basic (₹)**	15.88	17.63	18.13	17.48	16.86
Earnings Per Share- Diluted (₹)**	15.83	17.57	18.09	17.43	16.83

Financial position	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18
Share Capital	4,932	4,937	4,941	4,861	9,048
Net Worth	344,886	409,628	467,384	522,695	485,346
Gross cash (A)	187,258	251,048	303,293	344,740	294,019
Total Debt (B)	51,592	78,913	125,221	142,412	138,259
Net Cash (A-B)	135,666	172,135	178,072	202,328	155,760
Property, Plant and Equipment (C)	51,449	54,206	64,952	69,794	64,443
Intangible Assets (D)	1,936	7,931	15,841	15,922	18,113
Property, Plant and Equipment and Intangible Assets (C+D)	53,385	62,137	80,793	85,716	82,556
Goodwill	63,422	68,078	101,991	125,796	117,584
Net Current Assets	218,534	272,463	284,264	309,355	292,649
Capital Employed	396,478	488,538	592,605	665,107	623,605
Shareholding related					
Number of Shareholders [#]	210,471	213,588	227,369	241,154	269,694
Market Price Per Share (₹) ^{##}	271.60	314.43	282.13	257.85	281.15

8.SWOT ANALYSIS

SWOT Analysis is one strategic coming up with tool usually accustomed to asses the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats that is concerned either during a project or during a business venture. SWOT is additionally the tool aims to visualize wherever is that the real position of a company among the market and existing competition and to spot the key of internal and external factors that are significantly crucial to achieving the objective.

Strengths: Continuous innovation: Wipro Technologies has an efficient research and development facility that meets the global standards. In this regard, it continues to create new goods and services that attract the attention of new customers as well as shareholders in the market. The company has been able to achieve great milestones in product development. It has a vast customer base. Having a large customer base across the world gives Wipro an upper hand to increase its revenue due to its strong brand. For example, over 90% of its revenue comes from repeat business. Many businesses are in need of its software solutions, an implication that there is ever increasing demand for its services or products. Skilled employees: the HR practices at the company has made it easier for Wipro to remain its employees. For example, the recent changes in HR policies are suitable and sustainable for employees. The overall attrition rate has significantly improved over the last quarter. Economies of scale: the company also positions itself in the IT market as a low-cost provider. This strength has made the company to achieve a lot in terms of increased customer base. Economies of scale is allowed to clients who buy services or products in large scale. Customer satisfaction: this is made possible through quality product and delivery capabilities. Wipro Technologies gives quality a top most priority because it is committed to ensuring customer satisfaction. As a result, the clients have registered their satisfaction with the company. Eco-friendly products: innovation is the order of the day at Wipro Technologies, and it has enabled the company to gain value propositions. It advocates for reusable computer peripherals as well as less toxic material used in its production process.

Weaknesses:

Overdependence of mature markets: this poses a risk to the company because the domestic market is huge, yet it remains to be underdeveloped. Secondly, the company shies away from making a business investment. For example, it does not encourage joint investment with the customer. Instead, it prefers executing the business given out by the client. Strong concentration on the process: Wipro Company is very much focused on the process and not the people. As a result, delays have been common especially during decision-making process by the top management. Precarious top management: frequent changes in top management is one area that the company is doing badly. For example, the managing director has to abide by Premji's vision, and this gives rise to conflict in top management. Making changes in the top management disorients the operations of the middle and upper-level management.

Opportunities:

Consultancy area: Wipro Consultancy is believed to be one of the best in the IT industry. The company is therefore in a position to achieve more especially with its large customer base. Emerging technology: since it boasts of skilled employees, the latter can make good use of

technologies to create new products or services that satisfy the varied needs of the consumers . Huge global and potential domestic market: as a global company, Wipro can take advantage of global opportunities to increase its market share. On the other hand, it has the capacity to capture to domestic Indian IT industry, another opportunity to expand.

Threats:

The high cost of human capital: due to high attrition rate in the IT industry, recruiting people can be very costly. This can affect the profitability of the firm . Stiff competition. The level of competition in the IT market is very high. As a result, firms will always compete for the buyers. It requires a unique differentiation strategy in order to penetrate the market . Exchange rate: due to economic changes, exchange rates are affected either. For example, high exchange rates impact negatively on the firm's profits and vice versa.

9.BUSINESS OVERVIEW :

We are one of the leading providers of IT services globally. We combine the business knowledge and industry expertise of our domain specialists and the technical knowledge and implementation skills of our delivery team leveraging our products, platforms, partnerships and solutions in our development centers located around the world. We develop and integrate innovative solutions that enable our clients to leverage IT to achieve their business objectives at competitive costs. We use our quality processes and global talent pool to deliver ‘time to development’ advantages, cost savings and productivity improvements. Our IT Services business provides a range of IT and IT-enabled services which include digital strategy advisory, customercentric design, technology consulting, IT consulting, custom application design, development, re-engineering and maintenance, systems integration, package implementation, global infrastructure services, analytics services, business process services, research and development and hardware and software design to leading enterprises worldwide.

10.SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER INNOVATIONS :

- Rethink your high-level business strategy
- Collaborate with more technology-related industries and companies.
- Eliminates projects and proceses that don't work
- Recognize and protect Entrepreneur's
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11.CONCLUSIONS :

Wipro faced many barriers when it first started, the biggest as its CEO mentioned in an interview with Forbes was that they were looked as a joke being a consumer care company going into technology. That's why they changed their name from Western India Products Limited to Wipro. It was about the credibility. But they invested a lot in R&D and talent. Wipro put plenty of support money into building custom solutions and into building a strong after-sales service network that was not very prevalent in those days. Today the IT industry

is strong and so its Wipro. Wipro has presence around the world and even in Latin America where it has been difficult for them to acquire the experience. Wipro is a company that keeps growing, and expanding around the world. Wipro is doing recruitment from American, European campuses and are now starting Japanese campuses. They are setting up a center in Atlanta, where they will be recruiting from universities, and would like to build up to 500 people. They'll probably have two more centers in the U.S., typically in low-cost areas, university towns. Community sensitivity and visa concerns make this essential, and it makes sense to have a local cadre, apart from employees gained through acquisitions.

REFERENCES :

- [1] https://www.wipro.com/content/dam/nexus/en/sustainability/sustainability_reports/wipro-sustainability-report-2016-2017.pdf
- [2] <https://www.wipro.com/content/dam/nexus/en/investor/annual-reports/2017-2018/annual-report-for-fy-2017-18.pdf>
- [3] <https://www.wipro.com/en-IN/investors/annual-reports/>
- [4] <https://www.wipro.com/annual-reports/>
- [5] <http://www.annualreports.com/Company/wipro-limited>
- [6] <https://www.wiproinfra.com/wp-content/uploads/resources-pdf/wel-annual-report-2017-2018.pdf>
- [7] <https://www.marketwatch.com/press-release/wipro-annual-report-2018-on-form-20-f-available-online-for-ads-holders-2018-06-28>
- [8] <https://www.thehindubusinessline.com/companies/announcements/others/wipro-ltd-wipro-annual-report-2018-on-form-20-f-available-online-for-ads-holders/article24281330.ece>
- [9] <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wipro>
- [10] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An Effective Method of Developing Business Case Studies based on Company Analysis, International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME), 2(1), 16-27. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.400579>
- [11] Aithal, P. S. & Acharya, R. K. (2016). Strategic Management Models & Indian Epics, International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR), 5(4), 180-188, DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161093>.
- [12] Reshma, Aithal P. S., Shailashree V T, Sridhar Acharya, P. (2015). An Empirical study on working from home – A popular E-business model, International Journal of Advance and Innovative Research, 2(2), 12-18. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.164429>.
- [13] Aithal, P. S., & Suresh Kumar, P. M. (2016). Theory A for Optimizing Human Productivity, IRA International Journal of Management & Social Sciences, 4(3), 526-535. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21013/jmss.v4.n3.p2>.
- [14] Reshma, Aithal, P. S. & Sridhar Acharya, P. (2015). Relevance of On-line Office Administration through Working from Home in Future Education System. International

Journal of Application or Innovation in Engineering & Management, 4(4), 44 – 53. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163882>.

[15] Aithal, P.S., (2015). Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities –A case study of MBA programme plan of Srinivas University. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR)*, 4(12), 106-122. DOI:<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163884>.

[16] Aithal P. S., and Suresh Kumar P. M., (2016). Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 1(1), 278-284. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.161046>.

[17] Varun Shenoy and Aithal, P. S. (2016). Changing Approaches in Campus Placements - A new futuristic Model. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 766 – 776. DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.160966>.

[18] Aithal, P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, (2016). A New Model for Commercialization of Nanotechnology Products and Services. *International Journal of Computational Research and Development*, 1(1), 84-93. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.163536>.

[19] Shubrajyotsna Aithal & Aithal, P. S., (2016). Student Centric Learning through Planned Hardwork - An Innovative Model. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 886-898. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.61830>.

[20] Aithal, P. S. (2017). Industry Analysis – The First Step in Business Management Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 2(1), 1-13. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.810347>.

[21] Aithal, P. S. (2017). An Effective Method of Developing Business Case Studies Based on Company Analysis. *International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME)*, 2(1), 16-27. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.400579>.

[23] Aithal, P. S., (2017). Company Analysis – The Beginning Step for Scholarly Research. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(1), 1-18. DOI:<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.573769>.